

EXPERIMENTAL MARKETING IN TOURISM: CRAFTING MEMORABLE EXPERIENCES

Khidoyatova G.E.

Tashkent State University of Economics, Master's Student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14220084>

Abstract. *In recent years, the tourism industry has undergone significant changes, leading to the adoption of updated approaches. The effectiveness of traditional marketing methods has diminished, with the primary factor being the evolving needs and desires of modern travelers. Today, tourists are seeking not just to travel but also memorable, emotionally rich, and immersive experiences. To meet these needs, experiential marketing is widely used in the tourism sector. Experiential marketing is a type of marketing that focuses not only on promoting a product or service but also on creating experiences that emotionally engage customers. This approach goes beyond simply encouraging tourists to visit destinations; it invites them to interact, create personalized experiences, and share these experiences with others. Experiential marketing enriches the overall tourist experience, strengthens brand loyalty, and helps create competitive destinations.*

Keywords: *marketing, customer, product, advertising, tourist, experience, technology, brand.*

Experimental marketing primarily involves presenting a product or service to customers through direct experience. The goal is not merely to sell or promote the product, but to establish a deeper emotional connection with the customers. Customers should not be limited to merely observing the product or service, but must feel actively engaged on both an emotional and cognitive level. This type of marketing enhances all processes within tourism—ranging from travel planning to post-trip impressions—by improving the overall experience of the traveler.

Experimental Marketing and Tourism

The role of experimental marketing in tourism is becoming increasingly important. In previous years, tourism marketing primarily focused on advertising travel destinations, selling packages, and offering prices. However, today the industry is evolving. Tourists no longer seek merely to see or relax; they are in search of unique, emotionally enriching experiences and personalized services. Experimental marketing helps meet these demands. For instance, a travel destination may not only be attractive due to its natural scenery or historical landmarks. If the destination offers tourists interactive experiences through its culture, art, or gastronomy, they will feel a unique connection through these experiences. For example, organizing tours in Iceland that immerse travelers in the natural environment, such as hot springs or volcanoes, or providing opportunities to explore traditional art forms in Japan—these are all forms of experimental marketing. Such approaches alter the way tourists perceive their travels, linking them to new and meaningful experiences.

Impact of Experimental Marketing on Tourism

Experimental marketing in tourism focuses not only on the act of traveling but also on creating entirely new, emotionally enriching experiences for travelers. For instance, when people visit a location, they remember not only its beauty or historical significance but also the emotions

associated with the place. When emotional connections are established, tourists form a deeper bond with the destination, making the experience unforgettable for them.

Engaging tourists emotionally leads them to re-live their travel experiences or share them with other travelers. This, in turn, creates a loyal customer base for the destination. Additionally, experimental marketing helps establish destinations as distinct brands. Building a brand and associating it with a unique experience that attracts tourists not only elevates the destination but also enhances its international recognition.

Integration of Experimental Marketing with Technology

In recent years, advancements in technology have expanded the scope of experimental marketing. Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and interactive mobile applications provide tourists with the opportunity to experience destinations in an immersive manner before, during, and after their trip. For example, through virtual tourism, travelers can "experience" a destination in advance, allowing them to plan and prepare their journey in a more informed and engaging way. Additionally, AR technology introduces travelers to new and innovative experiences. For example, through AR applications, tourists can visually explore historical sites or monuments. These technologies not only provide access to information but also create more interactive and engaging experiences throughout the journey.

The Future of Experimental Marketing

The future of experimental marketing in tourism appears highly promising. Tourists are increasingly focused on their emotional experiences and personal needs. This, in turn, demands more personalized and innovative marketing strategies within the tourism industry. Additionally, the advancement of technology and the integration of digital tools provide opportunities to create richer and more memorable experiences for travelers. Experimental marketing helps enhance various aspects of travel—from cultural experiences to immersive experiences facilitated by technology. This not only increases tourist satisfaction but also strengthens the branding of travel destinations, making them more competitive in the market.

Conclusion

Experimental marketing in the tourism sector not only helps create memorable and emotionally enriching experiences for travelers but also fosters new, innovative, and interactive encounters. This approach makes travel not only more engaging but also attracts tourists and strengthens their loyalty. The development of technology and the application of new marketing strategies will elevate tourism to a new level, making future travel experiences more exciting, personalized, and emotionally enriching.

REFERENCES

1. Pine, B. J., & Gilmore, J. H. (1999). *The experience economy: Work is theatre & every business a stage*. Harvard Business Press.
2. Morgan, N., Pritchard, A., & Piggott, R. (2002). Destination branding and the role of experience. *Journal of Tourism Marketing*, 7(2), 11-30.
3. Tung, V. W. S., & Ritchie, J. R. B. (2011). Exploring the relationship between experimental marketing and destination loyalty. *Journal of Travel Research*, 50(4), 368-382.
4. Huang, S., & Hsu, C. H. C. (2009). Sustainable tourism and environmental approaches in Taiwan: An experimental marketing perspective. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 17(2), 215-232.

5. Leung, R. W. S., & Chiang, C. F. (2012). Destination branding and customer experience: Applying experimental marketing strategies. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 13(3), 263-279.
6. Gentile, C., Spiller, N., & Noci, G. (2007). How to sustain the customer experience: An overview of experience components for customer engagement. *European Management Journal*, 25(5), 395-410.
7. Shaw, G., & Williams, A. M. (2009). *Critical issues in tourism: A geographical perspective*. Wiley-Blackwell.
8. Tsiotsou, R. H., & Ratten, V. (2010). Future research directions in tourism marketing and management. *Tourism Review International*, 65(3), 32-44.
9. Buhalis, D. (2000). Marketing the future competitive destination. *Tourism Management*, 21(1), 97-116.
10. Zhang, H., & Tseng, L. M. (2011). The role of experimental marketing in the tourism industry. *Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 11(2), 157-171.
11. Hoffman, D. L., & Novak, T. P. (2009). Online flow: Lessons learned and future perspectives. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 23(1), 23-34.
12. Kotler, P., Bowen, J. T., & Makens, J. C. (2017). *Marketing for hospitality and tourism* (7th ed.). Pearson Education.
13. Cai, L. A. (2002). Cooperative branding for rural destinations. *Journal of Tourism Research*, 29(3), 720-742.
14. Keller, K. L. (2009). Building strong brands in a modern marketing communications environment. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 15(2-3), 139-155.
15. Vargo, S. L., & Lusch, R. F. (2004). Evolving to a new dominant logic for marketing. *Journal of Marketing*, 68(1), 1-17.
16. Cunningham, P. H., & Kitzinger, J. (2008). The role of social media and experimental marketing in tourism destinations. *Tourism Management Journal*, 29(4), 23-29.